

Case report about the Crime around the Globe: A Brief Overview About its theories and Way to reduce it

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Abstract

This is a brief article about criminal behavior around the globe. What is it? How does it develop and distribute around the globe? What are criminal behavior theories, types? Then crimes changes over years, and conclusion about how to diminish and reduce globally.

Keywords: Crime, criminal behavior, Crimes types, crimes changing, control crimes.

INTRODUCTION

What is crime?

A crime is an unlawful act punishable by a state or other authority. A crime is an illegal act, any illegal action that considered an offence and is punishable by law. The intentional commission of an act usually deemed socially harmful or dangerous and specifically defined, prohibited, and punishable under criminal law. A crime is an action or omission punishable by the law. (<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/cyber-crime-toolkit-development/41248>).

Criminal offences may gear towards some individual or individuals but also towards a community, society or the even state. From a nonprofessional's perspective, anybody using biological agent to cause harm or destruction of life literally commits a biological crime. (<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/cyber-crime-toolkit-development/41248>).

A deliberate act that harms another person physically or psychologically, damages or destroys property, or violates the law are crimes; a crime that calls for public criticism and punishment, typically in the form of a fine or jail sentence. This is distinct from a civil wrong (a tort), an action brought against a person and calls for restitution or payment of damages. (<https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/cyber-crime-toolkit-development/41248>).

How does it develops and distribute around the globe?

Crime Statistics around the globe:

Crime rates vary greatly from country to country and influenced by many factors. For example, high poverty levels and unemployment tend to inflate a country's crime rate. Conversely, strict police enforcement and severe sentences tend to reduce crime rates. There is also a strong correlation between age and crime, with most crimes, especially violent crimes, being committed by those ages 20-30 years old.

Countries with the Highest Crime Rates*

The countries with the ten highest crimes globally are:

1. Venezuela
2. Papua New Guinea
3. South Africa
4. Afghanistan
5. Honduras
6. Trinidad and Tobago

- 7. Guyana
- 8. El Salvador
- 9. Brazil
- 10. Jamaica

<https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/crime-rate-by-country>

Intentional homicides are estimates of unlawful homicides purposely inflicted because of domestic disputes, interpersonal violence, and violent conflicts over land resources, integrant violence over control, and predatory violence and killing by armed groups. Intentional homicide does not include all intentional killing; the difference is usually in the organization of the killing. Individuals or small groups usually commit homicide, whereas killing in armed conflict usually committed by cohesive groups of up to several hundred members and thus usually excluded.

- World crime rate & statistics for 2020 was 5.61, a 0.74% increase from 2019.
- World crime rate & statistics for 2019 was 5.56, a 3.65% decline from 2018.
- World crime rate & statistics for 2018 was 5.77, a 2.24% decline from 2017.
- World crime rate & statistics for 2017 was 5.91, a 0.69% decline from 2016.

<https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/WLD/world/crime-rate-statistics> .

Types of crimes:

1) Crimes against a person

Violent crimes or crimes against a person aggressively prosecuted. These crimes carry the most significant penalties and prosecutors seek the maximum sentences.

These acts of violence include, but are not limited to:

- Homicide (murder, criminal vehicular operation or manslaughter)
- Assault
- Criminal sexual conduct
- Robbery
- First degree burglary (burglary with a weapon or an occupied dwelling)
- Second-degree residential burglary (burglary of an unoccupied dwelling).

- 2) Sexual crimes.
- 3) Domestic crimes.
- 4) Child abuse.
- 5) Financial crimes.
- 6) Cyber-crimes.

- 7) Career crimes.
- 8) Mentally ill and dangerous people crimes.

<https://www.hennepinattorney.org/cases/adult-felonies/types-of-crimes-offenders>

Crimes in psychology:

First refers to as a criminal psychology, which is the study of the views, thoughts, intentions, actions and reactions of criminals and suspects. Criminal psychologists have many roles within legal courts, including being called upon as expert witnesses and performing psychological assessments. Some types of psychiatry behavior with aspects of criminal behavior. Several definitions are used for criminal behavior, including behavior punishable by public law, behavior considered immoral, behavior violating social norms or traditions, or acts causing severe psychological harm. Criminal behavior often considered antisocial in nature. They also help with crime prevention and study the different types of programs that are effective or not effective.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Criminal_psychology

Criminal psychology does more than provide a glimpse into a criminal's psyche. It also plays a role in how the law is applied. In the courtroom, legal practitioners require a grasp of defendants' motivations and actions in order to render fair judgment. Forensic psychologists, as well as other mental health professionals, often called upon to help clinically evaluate the mental states of people who break the law.

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/law-and-crime>

Psychology plays a role in police work as well. Criminal profilers—who aim to determine likely suspects through a mix of crime-scene analysis, investigative psychology, and other behavioral sciences—are often forensic psychologists or criminal anthropologists. Law enforcement agencies often rely on these experts to get inside the head of a potential culprit by identifying the perpetrator's likely personality type, lifestyle habits, and quirks.

Criminal psychologists study the behaviors and motivations of criminals. Criminal psychologists may also practice criminal profiling. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/law-and-crime>.

Law and Crime

The question of why people choose to commit crimes—often in the face of severe consequences—is at the root of criminal psychology, a branch of study that focuses on the intentions and behaviors of those who plan and carry out criminal acts. On the other hand, psychology itself, over the years, engendered significant changes in how legal experts think about the crime and the law, as well as changes in how the mentally ill treated by the criminal justice system.

Understanding Criminal Psychology

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What does a criminal psychologist do?

Criminal psychologists study the behaviors and motivations of criminals.

Why is criminal psychology important?

Criminal psychology findings may help identify suspects, potentially allowing authorities to prevent future crime or catch a serial criminal. On a larger scale, understanding what motivates criminals to break the law—whether poverty, personality, or otherwise—is necessary for creating the societal conditions that may allow them to stop.

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/law-and-crime>

The Psychology of Crime

Exactly why people commit crimes, and what could deter them from doing so in the future, is of great interest to psychologists and law enforcement officers alike. So far, extensive research points to a complex mix of genetics, personality, life circumstances, and environmental factors.

Psychologists also undertake research to understand how criminals choose victims, whether it is possible to protect oneself from certain types of crime, and what legal professionals and policymakers can do to stop crimes before they occur. Though great progress been made in understanding the criminal psyche, many remains unknown about certain criminals' motivations, as well as an element of randomness in who is victimized and who is not. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/law-and-crime>

What causes a person to commit crimes?

Some individuals commit crimes out of necessity; others are driven by anger, rejection of authority, a manipulative personality, or psycho. While stereotypes that all mentally ill people are prone to crime is not accurate, there are instances where mental illness—such as psychosis, substance abuse, or severe bipolar disorder—could influence someone to break the law.

How do criminals choose victims?

There is some evidence suggesting that criminals choose victims, at least in part, based on how they look or move. One study, for instance, found that criminals were more likely to label someone a potential victim if they appeared noticeably different from those around them or was moving in distracted, unusual ways. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/law-and-crime>

Criminal Theories:

The three major criminal theories have emerged after decades of research on the criminal mind. The psychodynamic theory centers on a person's early childhood experience and how it influences the likelihood for committing crime. Behavioral theory focuses on how perception of the world influences behavior. And cognitive theory focuses on how people manifest their perceptions can lead to a life of crime.

Psychodynamic Theory

This theory largely comes to us from the mind of noted psychologist Sigmund Freud. He argued that everyone has instinctual drives (called the "id") that demand gratification. Moral and ethical codes (called the "superego") regulate these drives, and adults later develop a rational personality (called the "ego") that mediates between the id and superego, based on this idea, criminal behavior seen primarily as a failure of the superego.

More generally, psychodynamic theory sees criminal behavior as a conflict between the id, ego and superego. This conflict can lead to people developing problematic behavior and delinquency. The challenge with this theory is it is difficult to test.

Behavioral Theory

This theory revolves around the idea that human behavior develops through experience. Specifically, behavioral theory focuses on the idea that people develop their behavior based on the reaction their behavior gets from those around them. This is a form of conditioning, where behavior learned and reinforced by rewards or punishment. <https://online.pointpark.edu/criminal-justice/psychological-theories-of-crime/>

If a person is in the company of those who condone and even reward criminal behavior – especially a figure of authority – then they will continue to engage in that behavior. For example, social learning theorist Albert Bandura maintains individuals are not born with an innate ability to act violently. He instead suggests people learn violent behavior through observing others. Typically, this comes from three sources: family, environmental experiences and the mass media. <https://online.pointpark.edu/criminal-justice/psychological-theories-of-crime/>

Cognitive Theory

Cognitive theory focuses on how people perceive the world and how this perception governs their actions, thoughts and emotions. Most cognitive theorists break down the process into three levels of what called "moral development." <https://online.pointpark.edu/criminal-justice/psychological-theories-of-crime/>

- Pre-conventional level. This involves children and how they learn the external consequences of their actions.
- Conventional level. This involves teens and young adults, who begin to base behavior on society's views and expectations.

- Post-conventional level. In those over the age of 20, the focus is more on judging the moral worth of societal values and rules and how they relate to values of liberty, human welfare and human rights.
<https://online.pointpark.edu/criminal-justice/psychological-theories-of-crime/>

In the area of crime, cognitive theorists argue that criminals do not develop moral judgment beyond a pre-conventional level.

All three of these criminology theories undergo constant scrutiny and revision, but they provide the foundations upon which current ideas based. <https://online.pointpark.edu/criminal-justice/psychological-theories-of-crime/>

Crimes Changes Over years:

16th and 17th centuries

The crime rate seems to rise in the 1500s and then fall in the mid-1600s. Suggested reasons, are:

- a series of good harvests in the later 1600s
- a slower growth in population
- the greater availability of work

Sometimes there were surges in crime rates, after a bad harvest, or the end of a war when demobilized soldiers came home, crimes rates also affected by wars.

As the middle Ages, theft and violence were the main crimes that existed in the 16th and 17th centuries. The most common crimes were the theft of small amounts of money, food caused because of property. Violent crimes were minority. These often focused on violent or new crimes, which led to a misconception amongst many that crime was increasing in this period. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

18th and 19th centuries

The rate of crime probably remained stable in the early 1700s. However, between a decade of years: 1750 and 1850 there was a significant rise in crime. This was the time of the Industrial and Agricultural Revolutions. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

The decade of 1810-1820 saw the most dramatic rise in crime. This was the time of rising food prices, synchronized with poverty, and unemployment after the end of the wars with France. After 1850, the crime rate began to diminish gradually. This linked with the new police forces, and the changes in the system of punishments. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

Minor thefts still account for around 75 per cent of the crimes that we know about in this period. Like previous centuries, violent crimes were a minority, perhaps only 10 per cent of crime. Despite the fame of some career criminals, such as Dick Turpin, first time offenders or occasional criminals committed most crime. Most of the convicted criminals were men under 30. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

Many people at the time believed crime was more common than it actually was. There was fear of revolution amongst lawmakers and fear of increasingly violent crime. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

20th and 21st centuries

In the early 1900s, crime continued to fall, as it had done since 1850. However, from 1950 upward the reported crime rate has risen quite significantly. The rate of increase in crime has been faster than the increase in population. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

There have been an increasing number of surveys of the population, which help us to gain an insight into unreported crime rates. One survey in the 1980s suggested there were three times more thefts than were reported to the police. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

However, in these centuries, the amount of unreported crime dropped down compared to earlier centuries. People nowadays are more enthusiasm to report crimes to the police, and the police are more consistent in recording all reports of crime. These factors look like the rise in crime has been more dramatic than it has been. Therefore, crime has increased, but maybe not quite as dramatically as the reported crime statistics might suggest. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z2cqrwx/revision/1>

Conclusion:

How to control crimes?

Crimes as a social psychological phenomenon in human societies, affected by many factors, which change it from time to time and geographically around the globe.

To control crimes, we have to focus on factors that motivate them, as economical one that increase crimes as a result of unemployment and poverty. Also, on personality psychodynamics that drive one in current circumstances to act a criminal behavior. Then the effect of globalization, how does it effect on crimes and violence.

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